

CHARACTERIZATION OF FATIGUE R-CURVES BASED ON G_{MAX}-CONSTANT DELAMINATION TESTS IN CF/PEEK LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The near-threshold growth of delamination fatigue cracks under different stress ratios was investigated with unidirectional CF/PEEK laminates. Tests of mode I delamination fatigue crack propagation were carried out by using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens. The crack growth rate decreased with crack extension under the constant maximum energy release rate (G_{\max} -constant) tests. The true growth law which is not affected by fiber bridging was obtained by the growth rate at zero-increment of the crack length from a series of G_{\max} -constant fatigue tests. Then, the increase in the crack growth resistance caused by fiber bridging was evaluated by the analysis of the change in the crack growth rate with the crack extension. Although the saturated level of this increase was almost the same both for the fatigue and static tests, the length of the saturation for this increase was much longer for the fatigue test than that for the static test. Thus, it is important to note that the R-curves under fatigue loading are different from those under static loading. The differences of the crack growth behavior and the stress ratio dependency between the G_{\max} -constant test and the conventional G_{\max} -decreasing test were discussed on the basis of the mechanism consideration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interlaminar strength is still one of the design limiting factors in composite laminate structures [1]. Improving interlaminar fracture toughness and resistance to fatigue delamination is an eternal topic in composite laminate structures because traditional two-dimensionally reinforced composites have no reinforcement in the through-the-thickness direction [2]. Several materials have been developed to enhance the delamination toughness both under static and fatigue loadings. These materials often try to modify matrix resin and microstructures.

Interlaminar fracture toughness values of toughened CFRP laminates often depend on the crack length [3]. One of the main mechanism for this increase is the stress shielding effect of fiber bridging [4]. Similar to the behavior under static loading, the delamination fatigue crack growth properties of CFRP laminates also depend on the crack length and the crack pass location [5]. Then, the characterization of R-curve behavior under static and fatigue loadings is quite important with clear mechanism consideration.

In the present study, mode I delamination fatigue crack growth tests were carried out under the constant maximum energy release rate (G_{\max} -constant) tests. The true growth law which is not affected by fiber bridging was obtained by the growth rate at zero-increment of the crack length from a series of G_{\max} -constant fatigue tests. Then, the increase in the crack growth resistance caused by fiber bridging was evaluated by the analysis of the change in the crack growth rate with the crack extension.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material and specimen

The laminates were made from prepregs of APC-2 (AS4/PEEK). The 24 ply unidirectional laminates of the nominal thickness of 3 mm were fabricated. The degree of crystallinity was 34% by using DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry). Tests of delamination fatigue crack growth were carried out under mode I opening loading by using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens (width = 25 mm, length = 120 mm) with a special loading device as shown in Figure 1. Initial cracks were introduced into the specimen by inserting thin polyimide film (Kapton, 13 μm) during molding.

Figure 1. DCB specimen and loading apparatus. Dimensions are in mm.

2.2 Fatigue tests

The energy release rate, G , was calculated using the modified compliance calibration method [3]. The stress intensity factor, K , was calculated using the relation between G and K as follows :

$$G=HK^2 \quad (1)$$

where H is a function of elastic moduli (E_{ij} , ν_{ij}). The H value for this laminate was calculated as $7.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$.

The tests were carried out in a computer-controlled servohydraulic fatigue testing system (Shimadzu 4880, 9.8kN) with our original software. Load cell of 490 N capacity was attached to the testing machine. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test was also carried out to obtain basic static properties. The crosshead speed was controlled to be 1 mm/min.

For fatigue tests, the stress ratio, R , of the minimum load to the maximum load was kept constant to be 0.1 and 0.5. The frequency of stress cycling was 5 Hz. The maximum energy release rate, G_{max} , - constant tests were carried out by calculating the maximum load, corresponding the constant G_{max} [6,7] The load-shedding tests were carried out by keeping maximum crack opening displacement constant. The crack length during fatigue tests was computed from the measurement of compliance by using the calibration equation of the modified compliance method. No precracks were introduced into specimens both under static and fatigue loading.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Static fracture toughness tests

Figure 2 indicates the relationship between the fracture toughness and the increment of fracture toughness. Here, different symbols show results from different specimens. The initial fracture toughness, G_{IC} , is determined using the point of deviation from the linearity in the initial load-

displacement curve. The data points at $\Delta a=0$ correspond to this initial fracture toughness. The G_{IC} value was 1170 N/m. The propagation values of the fracture toughness, G_{IR} , increased rapidly from the initial values when Δa is shorter than 2 mm, and then levelled off after $\Delta a = 2$ mm. The average values of the propagation value, $\overline{G_{IR}}$, was 1720 N/m.

This increase of the fracture toughness from the initial value is attributed to the formation and breakage of fiber bridging. Closure force of fiber bridging brings stress shielding at the crack tip. This mechanism can easily explained by the superposition of the stress field by the following equation.

$$K_{tip} = K_{ap} - K_{bridge} \quad (2)$$

where K_{tip} is the true stress intensity factor at the crack tip, K_{ap} is the stress intensity factor corresponding to the applied load, and K_{bridge} is the contribution of crack closure force to the stress intensity factor. When we suppose that K_{tip} is constant without respect to the increment of the crack length because less contribution of plasticity, the increase in K_{bridge} brings the rising R-curves at the initial part of the fracture toughness. Since the initial value is not influenced by fiber bridging, G_{IC} corresponds to K_{tip} . G_{IR} corresponds to K_{ap} during propagation.

Figure 2. Relationship between fracture toughness and crack extension.

3.2 Delamination fatigue crack growth under constant G_{max}

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the crack propagation rate, da/dN , and the increment of the crack length from the starter film, Δa . Except for the initial region, da/dN decreased linearly with the increment of the crack length when Δa is shorter than about 10 mm. The initial increase in da/dN is caused by the difference of the crack length and the growth rate along the crack front in the width direction. The crack propagation rate in this figure was measured through the compliance calibration method. This rate corresponds to the average crack propagation rate in the width direction. In the initial stage, the average da/dN was smaller than the actual da/dN at the center of the specimen in the width direction, resulting in the initial increase in da/dN for this figure.

Then, the maximum da/dN in Figure 3 does not correspond to the da/dN at $\Delta a = 0$. In the present study, the da/dN at $\Delta a = 0$ was determined by extrapolating the straight line to $\Delta a = 0$ as indicated in this figure. After $\Delta a = 10$ mm, da/dN saturated to a constant value. This saturation is only measured for the case of $G_{max} = 500$ N/m. Though similar saturation is expected for other loading condition, tests were not carried out for the saturation range owing to quite a long testing time.

The crack growth behavior in Figure 3 is roughly expressed by the following equations:

$$\log(da/dN) = \log V_a - \Delta a \log V_1 \quad (\Delta a > \Delta a^*) \quad (3)$$

$$da/dN = \text{constant} \quad (\Delta a > \Delta a^*) \quad (4)$$

Figure 3. Change in da/dN with Δa in G_{max} -constant test.

(a) $R = 0.1$

(b) $R = 0.5$

Figure 4. Change in da/dN with Δa under different G_{max} and stress ratio.

Figure 4 shows the relationship between da/dN values and Δa for all tests under two different stress ratios obtained in this study. Only the approximated lines are indicated in this figure. There is no significant difference in $\log V_1$ under $R = 0.1$ and 0.5 . Figure 5 indicates the relationship between da/dN and G_{max} for G_{max} -constant tests. The da/dN corresponding to the initial crack growth ($\Delta a = 0$) was indicated by solid marks. da/dN at $\Delta a = 0$ is expressed by power functions of G_{max} in the region where da/dN is larger than 10^{-9} m/cycle. The exponent of the power function under $R=0.5$ (4.9) is larger than that under $R=0.1$ (3.9).

It was difficult to obtain the da/dN which was extrapolated to $\Delta a = 0$ near the threshold region. Many data points down to 10^{-11} m/cycle region were obtained. Moreover, the da/dN values decreased below the limit of measurement during the tests, showing that the cracks were arrested. These facts suggest the existence of the growth threshold.

Figure 5 Relationship between crack propagation rate and maximum energy release rate in G_{max} -constant tests.

3.3 Analysis of crack growth resistance

Equation (1) is expressed by the following equation under fatigue loading:

$$\Delta K_{tip} = \Delta K_{ap} - \Delta K_{bridge} \quad (5)$$

where ΔK is the stress intensity range. When the true fatigue crack growth behavior is expressed by the following equation,

$$da/dN = C(\Delta K_{tip})^n \quad (6)$$

The relative contribution of fiber bridging under fatigue loading is expressed by the following equation [8]:

$$\frac{\Delta K_{bridge}}{\Delta K_{ap}} = 1 - V_1^{-\frac{\Delta a}{n}} \quad (7)$$

The relative contribution of fiber bridging under static loading is expressed by the following equation from equation (2).

$$\frac{K_{bridge}}{K_{ap}} = 1 - \frac{K_{tip}}{K_{ap}} = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{G_{IC}}}{\sqrt{G_{IR}}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 6. Change of fiber bridging normalized by applied stress intensity factor with crack extension.

Figure 7. Change of fiber bridging normalized by average propagation value of fracture toughness with crack extension.

Figure 6 indicates the results both under $R=0.1$ and 0.5 . Though scatter of the data was large, lower G_{\max} and ΔK_{ap} gave higher gradients of K_{bridge}/K_{ap} . While this initial gradient under fatigue loading is smaller than that under static loading, the saturated value of K_{bridge}/K_{ap} under fatigue loading is much larger than that under static loading. Thus, the relative contribution of fiber bridging under fatigue loading is much larger than that under static loading. It is also interesting to note that the saturated length of the contribution of fiber bridging under static loading is much shorter than that under fatigue loading.

The absolute contribution of fiber bridging under fatigue loading is expressed by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\Delta K_{\text{bridge}}}{K_{IR}} &= \frac{\Delta K_{\text{bridge}}}{\Delta K_{ap}} \frac{\Delta K_{ap}}{K_{IR}} \\
 &= \frac{\Delta K_{\text{bridge}}}{\Delta K_{ap}} \frac{\sqrt{G_{\max}}(1-R)}{\sqrt{G_{IR}}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{K_{bridge}}{K_{IR}} &= \frac{K_{bridge}}{K_{ap}} \frac{K_{ap}}{K_{IR}} \\ &= \frac{K_{bridge}}{K_{ap}} \frac{\sqrt{G_{IR}}}{\sqrt{G_{IR}}} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Figure 7 shows the results under $R = 0.1$ and 0.5 . It is interesting to note that the saturated value of the static fracture toughness test agrees with that for fatigue test under $R = 0.1$ and $G_{max} = 500$ N/m. Similar to that in Figure 6, the initial gradient under static loading is much larger than that under fatigue loading. The saturated value of K_{bridge} is decided by the balance of formation and fracture of fiber bridging. Since the strength of carbon fiber is insensitive to fatigue loading, the fracture of fiber bridging is not directly affected by the fatigue loading. Further researches are required.

3.4 Comparison between G_{max} -constant tests and G_{max} -decreasing tests

Figure 8 compares the results between G_{max} -constant tests and G_{max} -decreasing tests using the same laminates. Here, the load-shedding test was carried out by keeping the crack opening displacement constant. It is clear that G_{max} -decreasing tests gave non-conservative fatigue crack growth low near the threshold region.

Figure 8. Comparison between G_{max} -constant test and G_{max} decreasing test.

4. SUMMARY

Delamination fatigue crack growth tests were carried out using G_{max} -constant tests. The true fatigue crack growth resistance without respect to fiber bridging was obtained by these tests. The fatigue crack growth resistance obtained by this method is lower than that obtained by the conventional load-shedding tests. The contribution of fiber bridging, K_{bridge} , was analyzed. This value increased with the crack extension. While the gradient of this increase under fatigue loading was much lower than that under static loading, the saturated K_{bridge} was identical for both static and fatigue loading.

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